

MODERN REQUIREMENTS FOR THE SPIRITUAL IMAGE OF YOUNG PEOPLE AND ITS MANIFESTATION IN PRACTICE

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Abstract

The article deals with the socio-philosophical foundations of the dialectic of tradition and modernity in the development of spiritual and moral consciousness of students, objective factors in ensuring universal and national spiritual stability, scientifically based criteria for raising the spirituality of youth and the principles of creative thinking, non-standard decision making, strong civic position. the principles of internal and external dynamics of formation as a highly spiritual person, ways and means of raising the national educational paradigm (stratification, psychological analysis, social environment-based, cognitive approach) are scientifically based.

Key words: Youth, pragmatic thinking, ideological immunity, civic, creative thinking, non-standard decision, civic position, psychological analysis.

It is known that during the student period, young people have a strong desire and effort to learn about the world, philosophical observation, psychological analysis, logical thinking, and development of thinking aspects. At the same time, they have a tendency to fantasy, which in this physiological and psychological condition is considered a factor for developing thinking, striving for knowledge, and carrying out scientific research. This means that students have more pedagogical and psychological capabilities compared to children of other ages, and they have a strong desire to learn about the world. Therefore, it serves as the main stage in the formation of students as individuals. Students of the higher education institution are knowledgeable, curious, eager for knowledge, well-mannered, independent thinkers, and their internal needs are fulfilled to the best of their ability. The development of a student's personality has its own characteristics. This is especially evident in social studies. This is characterized, first of all, by their strong desire for self-improvement and the growth of their interest in studying. One of the most important characteristics of the student period is the development of the desire to think independently. Therefore, in this period, instead of giving only theoretical knowledge, it is necessary to focus on formation of reaction to various practical situations, more research, creative approach, development of thinking. In the world education system, philosophy and psychology are the methodological basis of every

discipline. Because all sciences are theoretically based on philosophical laws. Also, scientific thinking is closely related to human psychology and philosophical principles.

In particular, naming 2020 as the "Year of Science and Digital Economy Development" and 2021 as "Year of Youth Support and Public Health Promotion" in our republic is aimed at developing the spirituality of young people by involving them in science and education. For this reason, it is clear to all of us that science, education and upbringing are the cornerstone of development and the force that makes the country powerful and the nation great. Our tomorrow, the bright future of our country, is closely related, first of all, to the education system and the education we provide to our children" [1]. The problem of forming the spirituality of youth, determining moral destiny and introducing universal human values to the world is one of the eternal issues developed by many generations of researchers. There is a lot of scientific literature covering the topic of spirituality, includes a variety of definitions, interpretations, and research directions. The diversity of approaches to the study of this problem is mainly due to the lack of a generalized theory of spirituality. A scientific approach to youth as a special group of society, taking into account the specific characteristics of youth lifestyle and culture, is reflected in the works of many local scholars in humanities.

In the work of President Sh. Mirziyoev "From National Revival - Towards National Rise", it is stated that raising young people to become spiritually mature people, becoming truly enlightened and possessing a high culture is a continuous vital need, knowledge and high spirituality are needed to increase the knowledge and level of young people, and attract more young people to education. emphasizes the need to achieve [2]. It is not for nothing that today's young people need to master all aspects of science and these young people are called the future of our tomorrow. Since the 21st century is the century of science, technology and development, the demand for qualified mature specialists is growing by itself. Therefore, it is necessary to form inter-student competition among students in learning the knowledge in the educational process. Pedagogues have a great role in making the lesson process rich in interesting, meaningful and controversial discussions. If the lessons are conducted in a non-traditional way, students are given more freedom of speech, and a moderately organized controversial topic can attract students to the lesson, surely the interaction during the lesson will serve as a source of increasing student knowledge. Effective use of free time creates a unique foundation for the student's future. Libraries enriched with enough literature for

students are functioning in each educational institution. If students spend their free time enriching their knowledge in libraries and analyze the books they have read with their friends, share the knowledge gained from these books with their fellow students, and apply the knowledge they have gained to life, it is natural that this student will become a good specialist in the future. In addition, the student's participation in sports outside of the educational process has a positive effect on his knowledge acquisition. The role of sports in the health of every young person is incomparable. A person engaged in sports becomes mentally, physically mature and perfect. The fact that our students can devote time to both libraries and sports clubs shows that they use their time effectively. Both intellectually, spiritually and physically mature and well-rounded young people are the owners of our tomorrow. In fact, today, fundamental improvement of the education sector has become the demand of the times. Based on this demand, laws regulating relations in the field of education are being adopted. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" was adopted on September 23, 2020, and its purpose is to regulate relations in the field of education [3]. Based on this Law, the main principles, educational system, types and forms of education have been clearly defined, the rules on distance education established in it, the necessary knowledge, skills and skills by students using information and communication technologies and the Internet global information network aimed at remote sensing[4].

Provides inclusive education in educational organizations for children (individuals) with physical, mental, sensory or mental disabilities. Of course, reforms in the higher education system constitute a certain part of the reforms implemented in the field of education. In particular, in October 2019, the concept of developing the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 was adopted in our country.

This document was based on tasks such as the acceleration of intellectual development, training of competitive personnel, effective organization of scientific and innovative activities, and development of integration of science, education and production in order to strengthen international cooperation [5]. The content of the concept reflects the priorities of the reform of the higher education system of our country. In it, expansion of the level of coverage and improvement of the quality of education in higher educational institutions, introduction of digital technologies and educational platforms, involvement of young people in scientific activities, formation of innovative structures, commercialization of scientific research results, international recognition and

many other specific directions are defined. All this serves to raise the educational process to a new level of quality.

In conclusion, it can be said that the reforms in the field of education today do not lag behind the reforms in other fields in terms of their relevance and practical importance. Because it is the demand of the time to continue the reforms in this field on a larger scale. In particular, in the action strategy and 5 important initiatives put forward by the head of our state, the effectiveness of measures such as increasing the morale of young people, involving them more widely in the education system, directing them to reading, increasing the intellectual potential, self-thinking and worldview of young people, strengthening their ideological immunity, Issues such as patriotism, love and loyalty to the people, and the upbringing of a mature generation, occupy an important place.

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